

A STUDY ON THE CONSUMPTION PATTERN OF CHOCOLATES IN COIMBATORE CITY

Madhavan Radha Krishnan*, Dr. V. B. Mathipurani**, S. Selva Krishna** & Dr. D. Divya Prabha***

* Student, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Madhavan Radha Krishnan, Dr. V. B. Mathipurani, S. Selva Krishna & Dr. D. Divya Prabha, "A Study on the Consumption Pattern of Chocolates in Coimbatore City", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 22-25, 2019.

Abstract:

The main objective of the study is to help the students to develop ability of research of the products and practical technique to solve real life problem related to the products. In this grand research it has been attempted to analyze the needs and preferences of the customers and suggest them the most suitable product solutions, as well as it is also analyzed the brand awareness among the people. The conclusion is that the company should concentrate more on television for advertisement, as mostly people get attracted through television only and the company should concentrate on its price and taste as people are least satisfied with it these factors.

Key Words: Chocolate, Consumption Pattern & Coimbatore

Introduction:

All marketing starts with the consumer. So consumer is a very important person to a marketer. Consumer decides what to purchase, for whom to purchase, why to purchase, from where to purchase, and how much to purchase. In order to become a successful marketer, he must know the liking or disliking of the customers. He must also know the time and the quantity of goods and services, a consumer may purchase, so that he may store the goods or provide the services according to the likings of the consumers. Gone are the days when the concept of market was let the buyer's beware or when the market was mainly the seller's market. Now the whole concept of consumer's sovereignty prevails. The manufacturers produce and the sellers sell whatever the consumer likes. In this sense, "consumer is the supreme in the market". As consumers, we play a very vital role in the health of the economy local, national or international. The decision we make concerning our consumption behavior affect the demand for the basic raw materials, for the transportation, for the banking, for the production; they effect the employment of workers and deployment of resources and success of some industries and failures of others. Thus marketer must understand this.

Problem Statement:

Research work in management parlance is extremely important for a given close view of the relatives of the real life business issues. For any management student who is striving to perform outstandingly. It is of paramount importance that apart from theoretical knowledge he must also gain some practical knowledge. Survey report deals specially with providing an opportunity to management students to have some exposure in real business world. My study topic deals with Consumer Behavior and different factors that influence consumer to purchase a particular brand of chocolates.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the factors affecting the consumption pattern.
- To know about the customer satisfaction level associated with the product and the customer preference level.
- To increase customer satisfaction and recapture the market share by fulfilling the customer needs.

Scope of the Study:

As learning is a human activity and is as natural, as breathing. Despite of the fact that learning is all pervasive in our lives, psychologists do not agree on how learning takes place. How individuals learn is a matter of interest to marketers. They want to teach consumers in their roles as their roles as consumers. They want consumers to learn about their products, product attributes, potential consumers benefit, how to use, maintain or even dispose of the product and new ways of behaving that will satisfy not only the consumer's needs, but the marketer's objectives. The scope of my study restricts itself to the analysis of consumer preferences, perception and consumption of Chocolates. There are many other brands of chocolates available but my study is limited to two major players of chocolates leaving behind the others.

Research Methodology:

Survey Design: The study is a cross sectional study because the data were collected at a single point of time. For the purpose of present study a related sample of population was selected on the basis of convenience.

Sample Size and Design: A sample of 100 people was taken on the basis of convenience. The actual consumers were contacted on the basis of random sampling.

Research Period: Research work is only carried for 2 or 3 weeks.

Research Instrument: This work is carried out through self-administered questionnaires. The questions included were open ended, dichotomous and offered multiple choices.

Data Collection: The data, which is collected for the purpose of study, is divided into 2 bases

- **Primary Source:** The primary data comprises information survey of “Comparative study of consumer behavior towards chocolates”. The data has been collected directly from respondent with the help of structured questionnaires.
- **Secondary Source:** The secondary data was collected from internet, References from Library.

Data Analysis: The data is analyzed on the basis of suitable tables by using mathematical techniques. The technique that I have used is bar technique.

Limitations of the Study:

- Due to limitation of time only few people were selected for the study. So the sample of consumers was not enough to generalize the findings of the study.
- The main source of data for the study was primary data with the help of self-administered questionnaires. Hence, the chances of unbiased information are less.
- People were hesitant to disclose the true facts.
- The chance of biased response can't be eliminated though all necessary steps were taken to avoid the same.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Variables	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
Age	18-25	65	59.09
	26-30	23	20.91
	31-40	16	14.55
	Above 40	6	5.45
	Total	110	100
Gender	Male	85	77.27
	Female	25	22.73
	Total	110	100.00

Interpretation: 59% are from the age group of 18-25, 20.91% are from the age group of 26-30, 14.55% are from the age group of 31-40 and 5.45% are from the age group of above 40. 77.27% are male and 22.73% are female.

Willingness towards Chocolate by the Respondents:

Willingness towards Chocolate	No of Respondents	Percentage
Very Much	85	77.27
Much	12	10.91
Not Much	10	9.09
Not at All	3	2.73
Total	110	100.00

Interpretation: The above table shows about willingness towards chocolate by the respondents were out of 110 respondents 77.27% like chocolate very much, 10.91% like much, 9.09% like not much and 2.73% not at all like chocolate. Its inferred that most of the respondents like chocolate very much.

Preference towards Plain Chocolate by the Respondents:

Preference towards Plain Chocolate	No of Respondents	Percentage
With Fruit and Nut	23	20.91
With Nuts	56	50.91
With Caramel	23	20.91
Any Others	8	7.27
Total	110	100.00

Interpretation: The above table shows about preference towards plain chocolate by the respondents by the respondents were out of 110 respondents 20.91% prefer fruit and nut, 50.91% prefer with nuts, 20.91% prefer with caramel and 7.27% prefer other flavours. Its inferred that most of the respondents prefer nuts.

Discount on Chocolates:

Discount on Chocolates	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	98	89.09
No	12	10.91
Total	110	100.00

Interpretation: The above table shows about discount on chocolates were out of 110 respondents 89.09% said there is a discount on Chocolates and 10.91% said that there is no discount on chocolates. It's inferred that most of the respondents said there is discount on chocolates.

Rating of Chocolates:

Rating of Chocolates	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%	5	%
Price	22	20.00	32	29.09	12	10.91	25	22.73	19	17.27
Tasty	24	21.82	13	11.82	32	29.09	33	30.00	8	7.27
Packaging	44	40.00	32	29.09	6	5.45	16	14.55	12	10.91
Availability	44	40.00	42	38.18	16	14.55	5	4.55	3	2.73
Brand	16	14.55	67	60.91	13	11.82	6	5.45	8	7.27

Interpretation: The above table shows about rating of Chocolates on various factors were out of 110 respondents 20% rate 1 for price of the product. 29.09% rate 2, 10.91% rate as 3, 22.73% rate as 4 and 17.27% rate as 5. 21.82% rate 1 for taste of the product. 11.82% rate 2, 29.09% rate as 3, 30% rate as 4 and 7.27% rate as 5. 40% rate 1 for packaging of the product. 29.09% rate 2, 5.45% rate as 3, 14.55 rate as 4 and 10.91% rate as 5. 40% rate 1 for availability of the product. 38.18% rate 2, 14.55% rate as 3, 4.55% rate as 4 and 2.73% rate as 5. 14.55% rate 1 for brand of the product. 60.91% rate 2, 11.82% rate as 3, 5.45% rate as 4 and 7.27% rate as 5. It's inferred that most of the respondents rate 2 for price, rate 4 for taste, rate 1 for packaging and availability and rate 2 for brand.

Table Showing Viewing Advertisements of Chocolates:

Viewing Advertisements of Chocolates	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	82	74.55
No	28	25.45
Total	110	100.00

Interpretation: The above table shows about viewing advertisements of Chocolates by the respondents were out of 110 respondents 74.55% view advertisement of Chocolates and 25.45% don't view advertisement of Chocolates. It's inferred that most of the respondents view advertisement of Chocolates.

Recognition towards the Word Chocolate by the Respondents:

Recognition towards the Word Chocolate	No of Respondents	Percentage
Cadbury	62	56.36
Nestle	21	19.09
Amul	7	6.36
Parley	20	18.18
Total	110	100.00

Interpretation: The above table shows about recognition towards the word Chocolate by the respondents were out of 110 respondents 56.36% recognizes Cadbury, 19.09% recognize Nestle, 6.36% recognize Amul, 18.18% recognize Parley. It's inferred that most of the respondents recognize Cadbury on recognition towards the word Chocolate.

Chi Square:

Age * Willingness towards chocolate

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and Preference towards other chocolates

Preference towards Other Chocolates When Thinking Chocolates						Total
Age		Chocolates	Five Star	Perk	Other Chocolates	
	18-25	10	12	8	1	31
	26-30	32	23	11	3	69
	31-40	14	9	2	0	25
	Above 40	7	5	3	0	15
Total		65	52	29	4	150

Formula for Chi-Square:

$$\text{Chi-square} = \sum (O-E) \wedge 2/E$$

$$\text{Degrees of freedom} = (\text{number of rows} - 1) * (\text{number of columns} - 1)$$

$$= (r-1) * (c-1) = (5-1) * (4-1) = (4)*(3) = 12$$

Table value = 9.488 for degrees of freedom and 5% level of significance

Calculator value = 12.07

As calculated value > table value the null hypothesis is rejected.

The above table shows about the relationship between age and Preference towards other chocolates when thinking Chocolates.

Findings:

- Majority of the respondents are form the age group of 18-25.
- Majority of the respondents are male in our survey.
- Majority of the respondents like chocolate very much.
- Majority of the respondents like chocolates.

- Majority of the respondents prefer nuts.
- Majority of the respondents said that the price of the product is standard.
- Majority of the respondents said there is discount on chocolates.
- Majority of the respondents purchase 3 chocolate bars in a week.
- Majority of the respondents have tasted Chocolates silk.
- Most of the respondents prefer chocolates when thinking Chocolates.
- Majority of the respondents prefer tasty chocolates in Chocolates.

Suggestions:

- The Indian company Amul has to review its process so as to gain brand loyalty of the consumers.
- The chocolates whose expiry dates goes off should be replaced at once and fresh stock should be offered.
- The chocolate companies should think on the matter that why the consumers switch over to the other brands.
- The chocolate companies should put more & more emphasis on the taste and quality of the chocolate so as to gain brand loyalty.
- As factors other than TV and Newspaper are considered less so companies should use the print and electronic media for advertisement in large extent.

Conclusion:

The most important factor which is considered while purchasing any milk chocolate bars is Taste of that chocolate. They give preference to other factors also, but most important thing is taste. The buying behavior of consumers is also affected by the different type of advertisements. And the most influencing media is electronic media i.e. TV, and from reference group friends are at most influencing position. Quality is the most important factor which consumers consider while switching over to any other brand of milk chocolate bars. The buying behavior of consumer for different brands of milk chocolate bars is affected by various factors like price, taste, packaging, brand etc. 55% of the consumer check or consider manufacturing and expiring date while buying any chocolate. 45% of consumers don't go for that. This should be a matter of concern. The conclusion is that the company should concentrate more on television for advertisement, as mostly people get attracted through television only and the company should concentrate on its price and taste as people are least satisfied with it these factors.

References:

1. <http://www.chocolatesindia.com>
2. <http://www.nestle.com>
3. http://www.aphrodite-chocolates.co.uk/history_chocolate.htm
4. <http://www.google.com>
5. <http://www.chocolates.co.nz/carnival/index.htm>
6. Raja rajeswari, Kirthika (2016) "A study on consumer behaviour towards nestle products with special reference to Coimbatore city". Volume: 6| Issue: 3| March 2016 ISSN-2249-555X| IF 3.919| IC value 74.50.
7. Patnaik, Pradeep Kumar Sahoo(2013) "An empirical study on consumer behaviour towards Cadbury's India ltd and Nestle India ltd (A case study of male and female of Cuttack and Bhubaneshwar of Odisha)". Volume: 1| Issue: 1| September 2012 ISSN (online) pp 1-11.
8. Michaela Draganska and Dipak C. Jain (2008) "Consumer Preferences and Product-line Pricing Strategies: An Empirical Analysis" Stanford University, Graduate School of Business, Stanford, CA 94305-5015
9. Wong Foong Yee AND Yahyah Sidek (2008) "Influence of Brand Loyalty on Consumer Sportswear" Int. Journal of Economics and Management 2(2): 221 – 236
10. Neoh Chee Yeong, Osman Mohamad, T. Ramayah and Azizah Omar (2007) "Purchase Preference of Selected Malaysian Motorcycle Buyers: the Discriminating Role of Perception of Country of Origin of Brand and Ethnocentrism" Asian Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 12, No. 1, 1–22.
11. Kim-Hyunah, Yang-Ilsun and Heo-Eunjung, (2005), "Cause-effect analysis of brand equity factors in contract food service Management Company in college and university in Incheon area.", Korean Journal Nutrition. 38 (5): 395-403.